

typical high-spin d^7 octahedral compounds⁹. Linear relationship of magnetic moments with temperature reveals that both the isomers are simple paramagnetic. First two bands of $\sim 17\,029$ (ν_2) and $\sim 23\,128$ cm^{-1} (ν_3) in the reflectance spectra corresponding to ${}^4A_{2g}(F) \leftarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(P) \leftarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$ transitions of high-spin d^7 octahedral configuration are consistent with the stereochemical results. Values of $10 Dq$, B , C and β , which have been calculated using Konig equations¹⁰ are $\sim 7\,02$, ~ 851 , $\sim 3\,317$ and ~ 0.76 , respectively. In addition to these bands, metal $\leftarrow$ ligand charge transfer bands of high intensity and energy have also been observed. Higher intensity and energy of charge transfer band of fast moving cobalt(II)-A ($44\,444$ cm^{-1}) than that of slow moving B-isomer ($39\,215$ cm^{-1}) indicate their *trans*- and *cis*-symmetries⁹, respectively.

Room temperature magnetic moments (~ 1.84 B.M.) for nickel(II) complexes, which seem to be unusual, could be accounted for considering high-spin octahedral-low-spin square-planar configurational equilibrium in them. Such examples of nickel(II) compounds are not uncommon¹¹⁻¹⁴. Varying temperature magnetic measurements reveal that lowering of temperature favours the interconversion of octahedral geometry to square-planar in both the solids. Reflectance spectra, however, display four ligand field bands at $13\,514$ – $26\,315$ cm^{-1} attributable⁹ to ${}^8T_{1g}(F) \leftarrow {}^8A_{2g}$, ${}^1E_g(D) \leftarrow {}^8A_{2g}$, ${}^3A_{1g} \leftarrow {}^8A_{2g}$ and ${}^8T_{1g}(P) \leftarrow {}^8A_{2g}$ transitions of high-spin octahedral geometry only. β values (~ 0.81) reveal high ionic nature of metal–ligand bonds in the complexes.

For copper(II) complexes, which involve one spin-free electron in cubic as well as in non-cubic ligand field symmetries, magnetic measurements are not very reliable for distinguishing stereochemistries and in such cases electronic spectral studies could be more fruitful. For $\text{Cu}_2(\text{TGPA})\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, which displays three ligand field bands at $11\,363$, $11\,905$ and $15\,873$ cm^{-1} with high intensity component at $15\,873$ cm^{-1} , distorted octahedral stereochemistry may reasonably be proposed^{15,16}, whereas $\text{Cu}(\text{TGPA})\text{Cl}_2$ seems to possess square-planar geometry as it exhibits *d-d* transition bands at $15\,152$, $17\,094$ and $20\,202$ cm^{-1} with high intensity component at $15\,152$ cm^{-1} . Besides these characteristic ligand field bands, involving ${}^2A_{1g} \leftarrow {}^2B_{1g}$, ${}^2B_{2g} \leftarrow {}^2B_{1g}$ and ${}^2E_g \leftarrow {}^2B_{1g}$ transitions, three metal $\leftarrow$ ligand charge transfer bands have also appeared at $33\,333$ – $40\,000$ cm^{-1} of the spectra of the complexes.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Dr. G. S. Vashishtha, Principal, N. R. E. C. College, Khurja, for facilities.

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Equilibrium Study of the Complex Formation of some 3d-Metal Ions with Potassium Ethylene Hydroxyxanthate and Potassium Ethylene Dixanthate

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Manuscript received 29 December 1986, revised 15 September 1987, accepted 23 September 1987

EXTENSIVE physicochemical studies on the complex formation of potassium ethylene hydroxyxanthate and potassium ethylene dixanthate with 3d metal ions have been reported in our earlier communications^{1,2}. Presently we report the thermodynamic stability constants as well as thermodynamic parameters, viz. ΔG° , ΔH° , ΔS° and ΔCp° associated to the formation of Fe^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes with these ligands.

Experimental

Potassium ethylene hydroxyxanthate (PEHX) and potassium ethylene dixanthate (PEDX) were prepared by the reported methods³ with some modifications as described earlier^{1,2}. Fresh solution

of the ligands in double-distilled water was used. Stock solutions of ferric chloride, cobaltous chloride, nickel sulphate and cupric acetate were prepared in double-distilled water. The strength of the solutions was determined by the recommended methods⁴. Potassium chloride solution was used to maintain constant ionic strength. All the reagents used were of AnalaR grade.

tures, viz. 25, 30 and 35° (Table 1) At each temperature the value of thermodynamic stability constant ($\log K^\circ$) at zero ionic strength was computed from a plot of $\log K$ vs ionic strength. Stability constants were found to decrease with the increase of temperature and ionic strength. For both the ligands, stability constants were in Irving-William order⁵, $\text{Co}^{\text{II}} < \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} < \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$. Fe^{III} complexes were

TABLE 1—OVERALL STABILITY CONSTANTS ($\log K$) AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND IONIC STRENGTHS (I , mol dm⁻³) AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS AT 25°

System	Temp. (°C)	$\log K$			$\log K^\circ$	ΔG° kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH° kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS° JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
		$I=0.05$	0.10	0.20				
$\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}-\text{PEHX}^a$	25	9.63	9.60	9.56	9.65	-55.0	-46.7	21.1
	30	9.49	9.47	9.41	9.52			
	35	9.36	9.33	9.27	9.39			
$\text{Co}^{\text{II}}-\text{PEHX}^b$	25	8.01	7.98	7.91	8.04	-46.0	-19.2	75.8
	30	7.95	7.91	7.84	7.99			
	35	7.88	7.84	7.76	7.92			
$\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}-\text{PEHX}^a$	25	8.29	8.19	8.12	8.26	-47.0	-25.9	79.3
	30	8.16	8.11	8.04	8.19			
	35	8.07	8.03	7.96	8.11			
$\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}-\text{PEHX}^a$	25	9.08	9.05	8.96	9.12	-52.0	-36.3	81.2
	30	8.96	8.92	8.82	8.91			
	35	8.85	8.80	8.69	8.91			
$\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}-\text{PEDX}^a$	25	5.72	5.70	5.65	5.75	-39.0	-27.7	12.5
	30	5.64	5.61	5.54	5.67			
	35	5.56	5.52	5.44	5.60			
$\text{Co}^{\text{II}}-\text{PEDX}^c$	25	4.62	4.56	4.42	4.68	-27.0	-13.8	37.9
	30	4.58	4.52	4.37	4.64			
	35	4.53	4.46	4.32	4.60			
$\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}-\text{PEDX}^a$	25	4.76	4.70	4.59	4.81	-27.5	-15.6	31.4
	30	4.70	4.65	4.52	4.76			
	35	4.66	4.59	4.47	4.72			
$\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}-\text{PEDX}^a$	25	5.08	5.04	4.95	5.18	-29.0	-19.6	21.1
	30	5.01	4.97	4.87	5.07			
	35	4.97	4.92	4.81	5.03			

^aSystems have no λ_{max} in the range 360–960 nm. ^b $\lambda_{\text{max}}=510$ nm. ^c $\lambda_{\text{max}}=430$ nm.

Optical density measurements were recorded on a Bausch and Lomb Spectronic 20 Instrument. A Toshniwal thermostatic bath with an accuracy of $\pm 0.1^\circ$ was used for holding temperature fixed during optical measurements at 25, 30 and 35°. Ionic strengths (0.05, 0.1, 0.2 M) were maintained with KCl.

Results and Discussion

The wavelength region 480–520 nm was found appropriate for optical density measurements as in this region the complexes showed appreciable absorptions while the reactants showed negligibly small absorption. In order to know the number of complexes formed, method of Voughburgh and Cooper⁵ was followed. The study of composition by Job's method⁶, slope-ratio method⁷ and mole-ratio method⁸ showed the formation of 1:2 complexes with PEHX and 1:1 complexes with PEDX.

Overall stability constants ($\log K$) of the complexes were determined by the method of Voe and Zones⁹, keeping metal constant and varying ligand at different ionic strengths and at different tempera-

tures, viz. 25, 30 and 35° (Table 1) At each temperature the value of thermodynamic stability constant ($\log K^\circ$) at zero ionic strength was computed from a plot of $\log K$ vs ionic strength. Stability constants were found to decrease with the increase of temperature and ionic strength. For both the ligands, stability constants were in Irving-William order⁵, $\text{Co}^{\text{II}} < \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} < \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$. Fe^{III} complexes were

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (M.N.A.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

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Mixed Ligand Complexes of Manganese(II), Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Copper(II) with *o*-Ethylmercaptobenzoic Acid as Primary Ligand and Pyridine and Methylpyridine as Co-ligands

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Manuscript received 4 August 1986, revised 10 September 1987, accepted 23 September 1987

THE present investigation reports the synthesis and characterisation of mixed ligand complexes of Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with *o*-ethylmercaptobenzoic acid, a potential (OS) bidentate ligand as the primary and pyridine and α -picolin as the co-ligands.

mercaptobenzoic acid in minimum volume of dry dimethyl formamide^a. To this solution, ethyl iodide and potassium carbonate were added. The reaction mixture was stirred and allowed to stand overnight. The solution was then poured in ice-water when *o*-EMBH appeared as solid which was recrystallised in ethanol.

The complexes of Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with primary ligand (*o*-EMBH) were prepared by refluxing the ethanolic solution (20 ml) of the metal chlorides (0.01 mol) and *o*-EMBH (0.02 mol) at pH $\approx$ 8 for $\sim$ 3 h. The complexes separated on cooling the solution. The complexes were filtered, washed with water, ethanol, ether and finally air-dried at 80°. Cu^{II} complexes were light yellow and the Mn^{II} , Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes were brownish green, reddish yellow and green, respectively. Elemental analyses of the complexes correspond to the general formula $M(o-EMB)_2(H_2O)$.

For the preparation of the mixed-ligand complexes, the ethanolic solution of the metal chlorides, the co-ligand (L=pyridine or α -picoline) and *o*-EMBA in 1 : 2 : 2 molar ratio were refluxed at pH $\approx$ 8 for 6 h. The precipitated complexes were washed with water, ether and finally dried at 80°. Elemental analyses of the complexes correspond to the general formula $M(o-EMB)_2L$, where M=Mn, Co, Ni and Cu.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			μ_{eff} [*] B.M.	Λ_m ^{**} $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$
		M	S	N		
1.	$Mn^{II}(o-EMB)_2(H_2O)_2$	11.90 (11.95)	15.00 (15.05)	—	5.84	14.00
2.	$Mn^{II}(o-EMB)_2(Py)_2$	9.32 (9.40)	11.00 (11.15)	4.70 (4.89)	5.84	15.00
3.	$Mn^{II}(o-EMB)_2(\alpha-Pic)_2$	8.10 (8.94)	10.45 (10.59)	4.44 (4.64)	5.80	15.50
4.	$Co^{II}(o-EMB)_2(H_2O)_2$	12.46 (12.88)	13.98 (14.01)	—	5.00	9.5
5.	$Co^{II}(o-EMB)_2(Py)_2$	9.86 (10.16)	10.72 (11.08)	4.11 (4.89)	5.10	8.9
6.	$Co^{II}(o-EMB)_2(\alpha-Pic)_2$	10.56 (10.43)	10.86 (10.68)	9.96 (9.89)	5.08	9.8
7.	$Ni^{II}(o-EMB)_2(H_2O)_2$	12.90 (12.84)	14.11 (14.02)	—	3.10	11.8
8.	$Ni^{II}(o-EMB)_2(Py)_2$	11.01 (10.13)	10.96 (11.06)	4.75 (4.83)	3.08	11.2
9.	$Ni^{II}(o-EMB)_2(\alpha-Pic)_2$	10.36 (10.56)	9.86 (9.96)	4.65 (4.58)	3.06	11.60
10.	$Cu^{II}(o-EMB)_2(H_2O)_2$	13.70 (13.76)	13.70 (13.86)	—	2.01	16.50
11.	$Cu^{II}(o-EMB)_2(Py)_2$	10.76 (10.88)	10.80 (10.97)	4.50 (4.79)	2.00	15.00
12.	$Cu^{II}(o-EMB)_2(\alpha-Pic)_2$	10.30 (10.35)	10.44 (10.43)	4.50 (4.56)	2.00	14.90

*At 308 K. **In acetone.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. *o*-Mercaptobenzoic acid (*o*-MBH) was prepared by the reported procedure¹. *o*-Ethylmercaptobenzoic acid (*o*-EMBH) was prepared by dissolving *o*-

Results and Discussion

The elemental analysis, molar conductivity and magnetic moment data of the complexes are given in Table I. The low conductivity values of the complexes were indicative of their non-electrolytic